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PREGNANCY COURSE AND OUTCOMES IN WOMEN WITH UNDIFFERENTIATED CONNECTIVE TISSUE DYSPLASIA

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ANNOTATION

The article is devoted to the problems associated with connective tissue dysplasia (CTD), predominantly undifferentiated forms of the disease (nDST). The relevance of the topic is due to the high prevalence of this pathological condition. The generalized nature of connective tissue damage with the involvement of the reproductive system in the pathological process significantly affects the course of pregnancy and childbirth. Complications that may be associated with pregnancy, childbirth and the postpartum period in women with nDST and which cause a high need for surgical aids: amnio-, episio- and perineotomy, cesarean section are presented. Particular attention is paid to magnesium, which plays one of the determining roles in the complex biosynthesis of the extracellular matrix in the formation of connective tissue and in the morphofunctional state of fibroblasts. The methods used to detect connective tissue metabolism disorders (determination of the level of oxyproline and fibronectin in blood serum, pyrinx D and glucosaminoglycans in urine, etc.) are described. In view of the lack of reliable diagnostic (biochemical and genetic) criteria for nDST, special attention is paid to the need for an integrated approach to assessing the condition of patients using anamnesis data, the results of clinical, instrumental and laboratory examinations.

Keywords: connective tissue dysplasia, hemostasis, complications of pregnancy and childbirth, magnesium deficiency, endothelial dysfunction, markers of collagen breakdown, genital prolapse.

Течение и исходы беременности у женщин с недифференцированной дисплазией соединительной ткани.

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Статья посвящена проблемам, связанным с дисплазией соединительной ткани (ДСТ), преимущественно недифференцированными формами заболевания (нДСТ). Актуальность темы обусловлена высокой распространенностью данного патологического состояния. Генерализованный характер поражения соединительной ткани с вовлечением в

патологический процесс репродуктивной системы существенно влияет на течение беременности и родов. Представлены осложнения, которые могут быть связаны с беременностью, родами и послеродовым периодом у женщин с нДСТ и которые вызывают высокую потребность в хирургических вспомогательных средствах: амнио-, эпизио- и перинеотомии, кесаревом сечении. Особое внимание уделено магнию, который играет одну из определяющих ролей в комплексном биосинтезе внеклеточного матрикса, в формировании соединительной ткани и в морфофункциональном состоянии фибробластов. Описаны методы, применяемые для выявления нарушений метаболизма соединительной ткани (определение уровня оксипролина и фибронектина в сыворотке крови, пиринкса D и глюкозаминогликанов в моче и др.). Ввиду отсутствия достоверных диагностических (биохимических и генетических) критериев нДСТ особое внимание уделяется необходимости комплексного подхода к оценке состояния пациентов с использованием данных анамнеза, результатов клинических, инструментальных и лабораторных обследований.

Ключевые слова: дисплазия соединительной ткани, гемостаз, осложнения беременности и родов, дефицит магния, эндотелиальная дисфункция, маркеры распада коллагена, генитальный пролапс.

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DISFERENTSIALLANMAGAN BIRIKTIRUVCHI TO'QIMA DISPLAZIYASI BO'LGAN AYOLLARDA HOMILADORLIKNING KECHISHI VA NATIJALARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqola biriktiruvchi to'qimalar displaziyasi (CTD), asosan kasallikning disferensial bo'lmagan shakllari (nDST) bilan bog'liq muammolarga bag'ishlangan. Mavzuning dolzarbligi ushbu patologik holatning yuqori tarqalishi bilan bog'liq. Reproaktiv tizimning patologik jarayonga jalb qilinishi bilan bog'lovchi to'qimalar lezyonlarining umumiyashtirilgan tabiati homiladorlik va tug'ish jarayoniga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatadi. CDST bilan og'riq ayollarda homiladorlik, tug'ish va tug'ruqdan keyingi davr bilan bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin bo'lgan va jarrohlik yordamiga yuqori ehtiyoj tug'diradigan asoratlari: amnio-, episio- va perineotomiya, sezar bo'limi taqdim etiladi. Hujayradan tashqari matritsaning murakkab biosintezida, bog'lovchi to'qimalarning shakllanishida va fibroblastlarning morfofunktsional holatida aniqlovchi rollardan birini o'ynaydigan magniyga alohida e'tibor qaratiladi. Bog'lovchi to'qima metabolizmi buzilishlarini aniqlashda qo'llaniladigan usullar (qon serumida oksiprolin va fibronectin darajasini aniqlash, pirinx D va siydikdagi glyukozaminoglikanlar va h.k.) ta'riflanadi. nDSTning ishonchli diagnostik (biokimyoviy va genetik) mezonlari yo'qligi e'tiborga olinsa, anamnez ma'lumotlaridan foydalangan holda bemorlarning ahvolini baholashda integral yondashuv zarurligi, klinik, instrumental va laboratoriya tekshiruvlari natijalariga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: biriktiruvchi to'qima displaziyasi, gemostaz, homiladorlik va tug'ruqning asoratlari, magniy yetishmovchiligi, endoteliiy disfunktsiya, kollagen buzilishi belgilari, jinsiy a'zolar prolapsi.

Connective tissue dysplasia is a group of genetically heterogeneous and clinically polymorphic pathological conditions characterized by impaired formation of connective tissue in the embryonic and postnatal periods and combining a number of gene syndromes (Marfan, Ehlers-Danlos) and undifferentiated (non-syndromic) forms with multifactorial mechanisms of development. In practice, undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia (NCST) is especially common. In unlike syndromic forms, the manifestations of NCST are not so manifest and often go unnoticed. At the same time, the versatility of the connective tissue defect in NCST suggests a variety of visceral

changes, some of which may have serious clinical consequences. In particular, the generalized nature of connective tissue lesions with the involvement of the reproductive system in the pathological process cannot but affect the course of pregnancy and childbirth. However, this aspect of the NCST problem has not been sufficiently studied.

The aim of this study was to study the features of the course and outcomes of pregnancy in women with NCST and the possibilities of preventing complications of the pre- and perinatal period.

Material and methods

The study group included 56 primiparous women aged 18 to 32 years (mean age 23.6±0.49 years) with external and visceral phenotypic markers of connective tissue dysplasia.

External manifestations of the "weakness" of the connective tissue included an asthenic physique, some features of the structure of the skeleton and ligamentous apparatus (malocclusion, crooked little fingers, scoliosis, flat feet, myopia). Visceral phenotypic markers of connective tissue dysplasia were considered to be abnormalities in the development of the cardiovascular and urinary systems diagnosed during ultrasound examination, and varicose veins of the lower extremities, established during general examination (Table 1). On average, 1.4 visceral markers of connective tissue dysplasia were detected in the women of the main group, so the total amount exceeded 100%. The most common changes were microabnormalities of the heart – primary mitral valve prolapse and atrial septal defect.

The age-comparable control group consisted of 45 primiparous women without the above changes and obvious somatic pathology.

The reliability of differences in the incidence of the analyzed complications in these groups of patients was assessed according to the c2 criterion, the Student's criterion was used in the analysis of quantitative signs, and the Mann-Whitney criterion was used in the analysis of ordinal signs.

Results and discussion

Information on the peculiarities of the course of pregnancy and childbirth in women with NCST is contradictory. Studying pre- and perinatal outcomes in women with one of the most well-known visceral manifestations of connective tissue dysplasia, primary mitral valve prolapse, a number of authors noted a significant increase in the incidence of complications of childbirth and the postpartum period compared to somatically healthy women [1–4], while others did not observe a similar pattern [5–7].

According to our data, women with NCST were significantly more likely to have complicated pregnancy and childbirth (87.5% vs. 53.3%, $p < 0.001$). The prevalence of certain pathological conditions of the pre- and perinatal period in patients of the studied groups is shown in Table 2. In the study group, cases of late gestosis (including edema, nephropathy, preeclampsia and eclampsia), premature birth, birth injuries (perineal and vaginal tears), as well as other complications were significantly more common. In addition, women with NCDT had a greater volume of blood loss during childbirth: 348.2 ± 53.4 ml versus 310.7 ± 45.1 ml.

These complications have led to a higher need for operational aids. Delivery by caesarean section for obstetric indications was undertaken in 57.1% of cases in the main group and in 17.8% in the control group, amniotomy in 5.4% and 2.2%, respectively, episio- and perineotomy in 10.7% and 4.4%, respectively. All births ended with the birth of live babies.

Cases of fetal and newborn pathology in women of the studied groups were subjected to a separate analysis (Table 3). In women with NCST, intrauterine growth retardation and chronic fetal hypoxia were more common. In the main group, premature babies were born three times more often, the percentage of sick newborns was higher - 42.9% and 37.8%, respectively. In the structure of morbidity of infants born to mothers with NCST, ischemic-hypoxic damage to the central nervous system prevailed, congenital malformations (cryptorchidism, hip dysplasia) were somewhat more common. In addition, the study group had a lower birth weight (3633.3 ± 54.0 g versus 3990.8 ± 69.8 g, $p < 0.001$) and a lower Apgar score (7.5 ± 0.2 vs. 8.0 ± 0.1 , $p < 0.05$).

So, **women with NCST are more likely to develop complications of pregnancy and childbirth** and fetal and newborn pathology. However, the connection between the genetically predetermined connective tissue defect and the occurrence of this obstetric and perinatal pathology

has not yet been properly explained. It should be emphasized that despite the presence of the main group of microabnormalities of the heart and/or kidneys in the patients, none of them had circulatory insufficiency. Greater than NYHA Class I, renal insufficiency, or evidence of active urinary tract inflammation. Thus, the noted complications cannot be associated with somatic pathology, which is a visceral manifestation of NCST.

One possible explanation for obstetric complications in women with NCSTD may be the endocrine imbalance found in this category of patients. A number of studies have shown the prevalence of neuroendocrine disorders in the form of menstrual disorders and pre-commuting syndrome, a high incidence of hypoestrogenic hormonal phenotype and ovarian dysfunctions in girls and women with phenotypic manifestations of connective tissue dysplasia [8,9].

However, our attention has been drawn to another potential cause of ante-, peri- and neonatal complications in women with NCDT – **magnesium deficiency**. Recently, much attention has been paid to magnesium metabolism disorders as a significant factor in many pathological conditions, including connective tissue dysplasia and a number of obstetric complications.

Magnesium ions are part of the main substance of connective tissue and are involved in the regulation of its metabolism, while in conditions of magnesium deficiency, the ability of fibroblasts to produce collagen is impaired [10,11]. Magnesium deficiency in primary mitral valve prolapse has been confirmed [11–13], and the efficacy of magnesium preparations in this pathology has been shown in practice [14].

Magnesium deficiency, on the other hand, is associated with a wide range of complications during pregnancy and childbirth. In particular, a decrease in magnesium leads to an increase in myometrial tone and underlies premature birth [15,16]. Impaired magnesium homeostasis is given a special place in the pathogenesis of preeclampsia and eclampsia, and an obvious decrease in its level has been shown in many studies [17–19]. Low levels of intracellular magnesium may contribute to the development of arterial hypertension in pregnancy [19], and a link between the level of magnesium in erythrocytes and the value of blood pressure in the third trimester of pregnancy has been revealed [18]. Experimental and clinical studies have proven the ability of magnesium preparations to protect the brain in newborns [20–22], and it has been established that magnesium deficiency during pregnancy can cause intrauterine growth retardation [23] and worsen the survival of offspring [24]. The participation of magnesium in the process of delivery and the importance of its deficiency in the occurrence of adverse outcomes in the mother, fetus and newborn determine the widespread use of its preparations in obstetric practice.

The prevalence of late gestosis, premature, rapid and rapid labor, fetal growth retardation and damage to the central nervous system in the newborn established in the present study made it necessary to study the features of magnesium homeostasis in the examined patients. A study of the concentration of magnesium in the blood serum and saliva of pregnant women of the main and control groups was undertaken. The choice of two biological organism media as the object of study is due to the lack of a clear correlation between serum and interstitial magnesium content and the low sensitivity of hypomagnesemia in reflecting true magnesium deficiency [25,26].

As can be seen from Table 4, the levels of magnesium in the women of the study and control groups did not differ significantly, while the study of the concentration of magnesium in saliva documented the deficiency of this macronutrient in patients with NCST.

Theoretical data on the adverse effect of magnesium deficiency on the course of the pre- and perinatal period and the deficiency of this electrolyte in pregnant women with NCDT gave grounds to assess the effectiveness of magnesium replacement therapy in this pathology. A total of 15 women with a gestation period of 26–32 weeks with signs of NCST, gestational hypertension, and the lowest levels of magnesium in saliva were selected for treatment. The patients were prescribed a two-week course of magnesium therapy salt of orotic acid (**Magneroth**, Vervag Pharma) in a daily dose of 3.0 (2 tablets 3 times a day).

Even under the influence of such a short treatment with Magneroth, normalization of magnesium homeostasis was achieved: the concentration of magnesium in saliva reached 0.34 ± 0.02 with the initial 0.14 ± 0.02 mmol/l ($p < 0.001$). At the same time, there was a decrease in the level of

systolic and diastolic blood pressure by an average of 7.3 ± 1.4 and 2.4 ± 0.7 mm Hg, respectively, as well as an improvement in well-being in the form of a decrease in weakness and the disappearance of headaches.

Thus, the results of the study allow us to attribute women with genetically predetermined "weakness" of connective tissue, designated as NCST, to the risk group for obstetric and perinatal pathology. Magnesium deficiency can be one of the real factors in the development of complications of pregnancy and childbirth in this category of people, and replacement therapy with Magnerot can have a clear positive effect.

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